

Effectiveness of Health Education on Safe Sex Practices and Hepatitis B Vaccination Uptake Among Tertiary Students in Benue State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Effectiveness of Health Education Intervention on Safe Sex Practices and Hepatitis B Vaccination-uptake among Tertiary Students in Benue State, using a quasi-experimental pre-test–post-test control group design involving 216 students, comprising 108 in the intervention group and 108 in the control group. The objectives were to compare mean safe sex practice and HBV vaccination uptake between the intervention and control groups, the intervention group received a one-month structured health education programme, while the control group received no education. Data were collected using a validated and reliable questionnaire (overall Cronbach $\alpha = .76$) and analysed using descriptive statistics and ANCOVA at $p < .05$. Baseline scores did not differ significantly between groups. Post-intervention findings showed that safe sex practice improved substantially in the intervention group (mean = 22.46) compared with the control group (mean = 17.97), $F(1, 204) = 499.72$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .17$. HBV vaccination-uptake was significantly higher in the intervention group (30.5%) than the control group (13.7%), $\chi^2(1, N = 207) = 8.40$, $p = .004$. Overall, the intervention produced significant and meaningful improvements across the two domains, demonstrating that structured health education significantly improves HBV prevention outcomes among students. The study recommends that tertiary institutions institutionalize structured HBV education within their routine health programmes and orientation activities to sustain and expand gains in HBV infection prevention. However, the short duration or follow-up may limit long-term inference

Keywords: Health Education, Vaccination-uptake, Hepatitis B, safe sex, and intervention.

INTRODUCTION

One of the major public health problems affecting millions by causing liver damage, cirrhosis, cancer, and failure is Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) infection. The word 'hepatitis' is derived from the ancient Greek word 'heper', meaning 'liver', and the Latin word 'itis', meaning 'inflammation'¹“Thus, hepatitis simply means

inflammation of the liver (which is responsible for processing nutrients, filtering blood)”. However, when the liver is inflamed, its functions are affected adversely. Hepatitis could be caused by heavy alcohol use, some medications, and certain medical conditions². Oftentimes, hepatitis is caused by a virus which is referred to as viral hepatitis³.

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There are strains of hepatitis viruses, which are labelled A, B, C, D, and E. Among the five strains of Hepatitis disease, hepatitis B, which is caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV), is the most common and most deadly strain⁴. The burden of Hepatitis B disease is severe worldwide. It is a viral infection that causes liver damage, and it is transmitted through contact with the blood or other body fluids of an infected person⁵. Globally, it is estimated that approximately 400 million individuals are chronic carriers of HBV, and more than a million people die annually from its related causes⁶. Hepatitis B may occur with limited or no symptoms but often leads to jaundice, anorexia (poor appetite), and malaise.

The alarming risk factors for HBV infection primarily include sexual misconduct, drug usage, injections, tattoos, and body piercing. It is believed that using sub-standard injection techniques, such as reusing used, insufficiently sterilized needles and syringes, results in millions of cases of hepatitis B and C, HIV, and other blood-borne diseases worldwide⁷. The hepatitis B virus is the 10th greatest cause of death worldwide and is regarded as the second most common individual carcinogen after tobacco⁸. To reduce the incidence of HBV infection, the World Health Organization⁹ recommends strict adherence to preventive measures, which include the conscious efforts and behaviours undertaken by individuals to protect themselves and others from contracting or spreading the virus¹⁰.

Practicing safe sex is a crucial preventive measure against HBV infection, as the virus can be transmitted through contact with infected blood, semen, and other body fluids during sexual activity¹¹. Engaging in unprotected sex with an infected partner is a significant risk factor, especially when there are multiple sexual partners or a lack of awareness about a partner's HBV status. To reduce this risk, the consistent use of barrier protection methods, such as latex condoms, significantly lowers the chance of virus transmission during vaginal, anal, or oral sex. In addition, maintaining a mutually monogamous relationship with an uninfected partner and undergoing regular HBV screening, especially before entering new sexual

relationships, are important strategies.

Vaccination serves as a powerful and scientifically proven preventive measure against HBV infection by enabling the body to develop immunity before any exposure to the virus occurs. The hepatitis B vaccine contains a non-infectious component of the virus, usually the hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg), which prompts the immune system to produce protective antibodies without causing disease¹². There are several licensed vaccines available for HBV prevention, including Engerix-B, Recombivax HB, and HEPLISAV-B, which are commonly used in different age groups and risk categories¹³. When administered correctly, HBV vaccination provides long-term protection, significantly reducing the risk of acute and chronic HBV infections and helping to curb the spread of the virus at both individual and population levels¹⁴. Safe sex practices, when combined with vaccination and responsible sexual behaviour, can provide a strong line of defense against the sexual transmission of HBV¹⁵.

Health education is a systematic process of providing individuals and communities with information, skills, and motivation needed to make informed decisions that promote and maintain healthy behaviours¹⁶. In the context of HBV infection, health education plays a central role in increasing awareness about the disease, its modes of transmission, the health consequences of infection, and effective methods of prevention. By enhancing the knowledge and practice of prevention, health education serves as a tool to reduce the spread of HBV and to promote early preventive action, such as vaccination and risk avoidance behaviours. For instance, a quasi-experimental study by a researcher in Northern Nigeria demonstrated that a health education intervention significantly improved the KAP of university students regarding HBV prevention, leading to increased vaccination rates and safer behaviours¹⁷.

Several other studies have demonstrated that health education enhanced HBV infection prevention practices among students^{18,19, 20,21}. Most studies conducted in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African countries have assessed the level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to HBV prevention among different population

groups, including students^{22,2,25}. These studies have consistently revealed varying degrees of poor knowledge and unfavourable attitudes toward HBV, as well as low uptake of preventive measures such as vaccination and safe sex practices. Despite the documented challenges, most of these existing studies have primarily been cross-sectional in nature, offering a snapshot of the prevailing knowledge and practices without assessing the impact of specific interventions. This presents a significant gap in the literature, as few quasi-experimental or controlled intervention studies have evaluated behavioural and vaccination outcomes simultaneously among Nigerian tertiary students, particularly in Benue State. Limited studies have rigorously evaluated the outcomes of health education interventions designed to improve HBV prevention among students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria^{19,18}. Given the high prevalence of HBV in Benue State and the strategic importance of the students' characteristics in disease control efforts, there is a pressing need to assess whether health education can meaningfully enhance students' improvement in safe sex practice as a means of preventing HBV infection^{26,27}. This study, therefore, addressed this gap by implementing and evaluating a health education intervention tailored to the needs of students in tertiary institutions in Benue State.

Problem Statement

Ideally, students in tertiary institutions, as members of the educated segments of the population, are expected to have adequate knowledge of major public health threats, such as HBV infection. With access to formal education, digital information, and health services, the students should demonstrate high levels of awareness about HBV transmission, symptoms, and preventive practices. They are also expected to adopt positive health behaviours such as getting vaccinated, avoiding risky sexual practices, insisting on the use of sterilized equipment for tattoos or piercings, and refraining from sharing sharp objects.

However, the reality among students in many Nigerian tertiary institutions, including those in Benue State, falls short of this idea. Evidence suggests that many students

engage in risky practices that expose them to HBV infection, including engaging in unprotected sex. Alarming, many students are unaware of their HBV status and have not been vaccinated, even when vaccines are available at minimal or no cost in public health facilities. The gap between what should be and what currently exists highlights a significant public health challenge.

Most studies conducted in Benue State so far have focused on assessing awareness levels without implementing or evaluating solutions^{23,28}. Therefore, there is a pressing need for an intervention study that not only assesses but also actively improves the knowledge and practices of students regarding HBV prevention. This study, therefore, assessed the effectiveness of a health education intervention in safe sex practice and vaccination uptake for HBV infection prevention among students of tertiary institutions in Benue State.

Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the mean difference in safe sex practice scores between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group).
2. Compare the proportion of HBV vaccination uptake between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group).

Research Questions The study answered the following questions:

1. What is the mean difference in safe sex practice scores between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group)?
2. What is the difference in the proportion of HBV vaccination uptake between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group)?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

1. There is no significant mean difference in safe sex practice scores between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group).
2. There is no significant difference in the proportion of HBV vaccination uptake between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group).

Methodology

A quasi-experimental design with a non-randomized control group pre-test and post-test approach was used to evaluate the effect of a structured health education intervention on safe sex practices and hepatitis B vaccination among tertiary institution students in Benue State, Nigeria. Two comparable groups were involved: an intervention group that received the health education programme and a control group that did not. Both groups were assessed at baseline and after the intervention using the same measures, enabling comparison of changes over time and between groups.

The study was conducted among students of public tertiary institutions in Benue State. The study population comprised 64,807 students, from which a sample of 216 participants (108 per group), 207 respondents completed the study. This was determined using a formula for comparing means between two independent groups, based on a 95% confidence level, 80% power, and allowance for 10% attrition.

A multistage sampling technique was employed to select participants. Six institutions were purposively selected across universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education, with one institution from each category assigned to the intervention group and another to the control group. Proportionate sampling was used to allocate the sample size across the selected institutions based on their student populations. Stratified sampling ensured representation across departments and levels of study, followed by simple random sampling to select participants within each stratum. Only full-time non-health science students were included to reduce

potential bias from prior exposure to HBV-related information. Participants were assigned to groups based on their institutions, and only those in the intervention group received the health education intervention during the study period.

The Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of HBV Infection Prevention Questionnaire was developed by the researcher and used for data collection. The instrument comprised four sections. Section A obtained sociodemographic information. Section B assessed knowledge of HBV prevention with items specifically addressing vaccination and safe sexual practices, using a three-point response format of True, False, and Not Sure. Section C measured attitudes toward HBV prevention, with emphasis on vaccination and safe sexual behaviour, using a four-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Section D evaluated preventive practices, focusing on safe sex practices and vaccination uptake. Items on safe sex practices covered behaviours such as consistent condom use, discussion of infection status with partners, and limiting sexual partners, while vaccination items assessed uptake of the hepatitis B vaccine. Practice items were rated on a four-point scale from never to always, while vaccination status was assessed with a yes or no response.

The instrument was validated by a panel of five experts comprising specialists in health education, science education, and test and measurement, who assessed the clarity, relevance, and adequacy of the items in relation to safe sex practices and vaccination. Their suggestions were incorporated to improve the content validity of the instrument. Reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot test among 50 undergraduate students outside the study area. The data obtained were analysed using Cronbach's alpha to determine internal consistency. The results yielded acceptable reliability coefficients for the subscales measuring safe sex practices and vaccination, with values exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.70, indicating good internal consistency.

The intervention consisted of a structured health education programme delivered over four weeks in the

intervention institutions. The sessions focused specifically on promoting safe sexual practices and improving hepatitis B vaccination uptake. Participants were educated on correct and consistent condom use, reduction of multiple sexual partnerships, and communication with sexual partners regarding infection status. Emphasis was also placed on the importance of hepatitis B vaccination, the vaccination schedule, and access to vaccination services. Interactive teaching methods such as lectures, discussions, demonstrations, and educational materials were used to enhance understanding and behavioural change. The control group did not receive the intervention during the study period.

Data were collected using the questionnaire administered before and after the intervention to both groups. Completed questionnaires were coded and analysed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarise participants' characteristics and responses on safe sex practices and vaccination. Analysis of covariance was used to test for differences in post-intervention scores between groups while controlling for baseline values, with statistical significance set at $p < .05$. The association between group membership and vaccination uptake

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants in the Intervention and Control Groups

Demographic Variable	Intervention	Control
	n (%)	n (%)
Gender		
Male	66 (62.9)	64 (62.7)
Female	39 (37.1)	38 (37.3)
Total	105 (100)	102 (100)
Age Range (in yrs)		
18 – 22	16 (15.2)	25 (24.5)
23 – 27	61 (58.1)	45 (44.1)
28 & above	28 (26.7)	32 (31.4)
Total	105 (100)	102 (100)
Marital Status		
Single	81 (77.1)	81 (79.4)
Married	22 (21.0)	14 (13.7)
Divorced/Widowed	2 (1.9)	7 (6.9)
Total	105 (100)	102 (100)
Institution Type		
College of Education	12 (11.4)	10 (9.8)
Polytechnic	16 (15.2)	6 (5.9)
University	77 (73.7)	86 (84.3)
Total	105 (100)	102 (100)

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of participants in the intervention (n = 105) and control (n = 102) groups. Gender distribution was comparable across groups, with males representing 62.9% of the intervention group and 62.7% of the control group, while females accounted for 37.1% and 37.3%, respectively. Participants' ages were categorized into three ranges. In the intervention group, most participants (58.1%) were between 23 and 27 years, followed by those aged 28 years and above (26.7%), and

those aged 18 to 22 years (15.2%). In the control group, 44.1% were between 23 and 27 years, 31.4% were 28 years and above, and 24.5% were between 18 and 22 years.

Regarding marital status, the majority of participants in both groups were single, comprising 77.1% of the intervention group and 79.4% of the control group. Married participants represented 21.0% of the intervention group and 13.7% of the control group,

while divorced or widowed participants made up 1.9% and 6.9%, respectively. With respect to institution type, most participants were from universities, accounting for 73.7% of the intervention group and 84.3% of the control group. Participants from polytechnics constituted 15.2% of the intervention group and 5.9% of

the control group, whereas those from colleges of education represented 11.4% and 9.8%, respectively.

Overall, the demographic profiles of both groups show a broadly similar distribution across gender, marital status, and institution type, with some variation in age range proportions.

Table 2: Mean Difference in Safe Sex Practice Scores between Students in the Intervention and Control Groups

S/N	Item	Status	Intervention		Control		Mean Diff.
			(n = 105)		(n = 102)		
			M	SD	M	SD	
5	How often do you use a condom during sexual intercourse?	Pre-test	2.41	0.72	2.31	0.73	0.72
		Post-test	2.98	0.55	2.26	0.73	
6	How often do you discuss your HBV or STI status with your sexual partner(s)?	Pre-test	2.09	0.75	2.04	0.72	0.98
		Post-test	3.06	0.57	2.08	0.68	
7	How often do you ensure your sexual partner uses protection?	Pre-test	2.18	0.82	2.18	0.80	0.83
		Post-test	3.07	0.43	2.24	0.77	
8	How often do you limit the number of sexual partners to reduce HBV risk?	Pre-test	2.39	0.83	2.44	0.80	0.64
		Post-test	3.14	0.56	2.50	0.74	
9	How often do you get tested for HBV or other sexually transmitted infections?	Pre-test	2.12	0.84	2.17	0.81	0.89
		Post-test	3.11	0.56	2.22	0.77	
10	How often do you avoid sexual contact when you or your partner has open sores or cuts?	Pre-test	2.60	0.63	2.55	0.61	0.84
		Post-test	3.43	0.50	2.59	0.57	
11	How often do you avoid the use of sex-enhancing drugs?	Pre-test	2.60	0.61	2.57	0.62	0.70
		Post-test	3.31	0.52	2.61	0.60	
12	How often do you avoid kissing a partner whose HBV status is not known to you?	Pre-test	2.50	0.73	2.56	0.66	0.58
		Post-test	3.19	0.48	2.61	0.64	
Average Total		Pre-test	17.79	1.57	17.57	1.62	
		Post-test	22.46	1.37	17.97	1.52	4.49

Note. M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, n = number of participants in a group

Table 2 presents the safe sex practice scores for students in the intervention and control groups before and after the intervention. At pre-intervention, the intervention group had a mean score of 17.79 (SD = 1.57), which was similar to the control group's mean score of 17.57 (SD = 1.62). After the intervention, the intervention group's mean score increased to 22.46 (SD = 1.37), whereas the control group's mean score showed only a slight

increase to 17.97 (SD = 1.52). The mean difference of 4.49 represents the difference in post-intervention safe sex practice scores between the intervention and control groups, indicating that students in the intervention group reported higher levels of safe sex practices compared with those in the control group following the structured health education intervention. This result is also illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Estimated marginal means of post-intervention Safe Sex Practice scores for the Intervention and Control Groups

Research Question 2: What is the difference in the proportion of HBV vaccination-uptake between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group)

Table 3: Difference in the Proportion of HBV Vaccination Uptake between Students in the Intervention and Control Groups

Group	n	Pre-intervention		Post-intervention		% Difference
		Vaccinated n (%)	Not Vaccinated n (%)	Vaccinated n (%)	Not Vaccinated n (%)	
Intervention	105	11 (10.5)	94 (89.5)	32 (30.5)	73 (69.5)	17.2
Control	102	10 (9.8)	92 (90.2)	14 (13.7)	88 (86.3)	

Note. n = Number of participants, % = Percentage

Table 3 presents the proportions of HBV vaccination uptake among students in the intervention and control groups before and after the structured health education. At pre-intervention, the intervention group had 11 students (10.5%) vaccinated and 94 (89.5%) not vaccinated, while the control group showed a similar distribution with 10 students (9.8%) vaccinated and 92 (90.2%) not vaccinated.

At post-intervention, the proportion of vaccinated students in the intervention group increased to 32 (30.5%), with 73 students (69.5%) remaining unvaccinated. In the control group, 14 students (13.7%)

were vaccinated, and 88 (86.3%) were not vaccinated. The difference of 17.2% represents the change in vaccination-uptake between the intervention and control groups at post-intervention, indicating that students who received structured health education initiated HBV vaccination more than those who did not receive the education.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant mean difference in safe sex practice scores between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group).

Table 4: ANCOVA Summary for Adjusted HBV Safe Sex Practice Scores between Groups

Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P	Partial η^2
Corrected Model	2357.40	2	1178.70	302.29	< .001	.75
Intercept	1507.54	1	1507.54	386.62	< .001	.66
Baseline Safe Sex Practice (Covariate)	395.59	1	395.59	101.45	< .001	.33
Group	1948.55	1	1948.55	499.72	< .001	.17
Error	795.45	204	3.90			
Total	105820.00	207				
Corrected Total	3152.85	206				

Note. SS = sum of squares; MS = mean square. $R^2 = .748$ (Adjusted $R^2 = .745$).

Table 4 presents the ANCOVA results examining whether there was a significant difference in post-intervention safe sex practice scores between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group), after controlling for baseline safe sex practice scores. The covariate (baseline safe sex practice score) was significantly associated with post-intervention scores, $F(1, 204) = 101.45$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .33$, indicating that approximately 33% of the variance in post-intervention safe sex practice scores was explained by initial differences in baseline scores, representing a large effect.

After adjusting for baseline safe sex practice scores, there was a significant main effect of group on post-

intervention scores, $F(1, 204) = 499.72$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .17$. This effect size indicates that 17% of the variance in post-intervention safe sex practice scores was attributable to the intervention. Students who received structured health education demonstrated significantly higher safe sex practice scores compared with those in the control group. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant mean difference in safe sex practice scores between the intervention and control groups is rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the proportion of HBV vaccination uptake between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention (intervention group) and those who did not (control group).

Table 5: Chi-Square Test of HBV Vaccination Uptake by Group

Test	χ^2	Df	p (2-tailed)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.40	1	.004
Continuity Correction	7.46	1	.006
Likelihood Ratio	8.59	1	.003
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.36	1	.004
Fisher's Exact Test			.004

Note. N = 207. No cell had an expected count less than 5 (minimum expected count = 22.67).

Table 5 presents the results of a Pearson chi-square test examining the significance difference in the proportion of HBV vaccination uptake between students who received structured health education on HBV prevention and those who did not. The association was significant, $\chi^2 (1, N = 207) = 8.40, p = .004$, indicating that the proportion of students who received the HBV vaccination differed significantly between the intervention and control groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the proportion of vaccination uptake between the intervention and the control groups is rejected.

DISCUSSION

The first finding of this study showed a substantial improvement in safe sex practices among students who received the structured health education intervention compared with those in the control group. At baseline, both groups demonstrated similar levels of safe sex practices, with the intervention group having a mean score of 17.79 (SD = 1.57) and the control group 17.57 (SD = 1.62). This close similarity at pre-intervention established that both groups started at comparable levels, allowing any observed differences after the intervention to be attributed to the educational programme rather than pre-existing behavioural differences. After the intervention, the intervention group's mean safe sex practice score increased markedly to 22.46 (SD = 1.37), while the control group experienced only a minimal rise to 17.97 (SD = 1.52). The resulting mean difference of 4.49 in post-intervention scores illustrated that students exposed to structured health education reported significantly better safe sex behaviour compared with the control group.

The hypothesis test further supported this finding. After adjusting for baseline safe sex practice scores using ANOVA, the analysis revealed a significant main effect

of group on post-intervention scores, $F (1, 204) = 499.72, p < .001$, with a very large partial η^2 of .17. This effect size indicates that 17% of the variance in safe sex practice outcomes was directly attributable to the intervention an exceptionally strong effect in behavioural research. Such a high magnitude suggests that the structured health education profoundly influenced students' adoption of safer sexual practices. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which stated that no significant mean difference would exist between the intervention and control groups, was rejected. This confirms that the intervention was highly effective in promoting behaviours that reduce the risk of HBV transmission through sexual contact.

These results aligned with findings from²¹, who also demonstrated the powerful influence of structured education on sexual behaviour. In their cluster randomized controlled trial among adolescent girls in Northern Ghana, a one-month Health Belief Model-based abstinence education programme led to a substantial increase in abstinence rates, 97.3% in the intervention group versus 84.4% in controls. Despite differences in behavioural targets (sexual abstinence versus safe sex practices), both studies showed that theory-driven health educational interventions can significantly shape sexual behaviours. The magnitude of behavioural change in both studies also highlighted how structured, well-delivered education meaningfully improves protective sexual practices. However²¹ focused on preventing adolescent pregnancy and promoting abstinence, whereas the present study centered specifically on safe sex as a mechanism for preventing HBV transmission among tertiary institution students.

The present findings also shared similarities with those of a researcher, who explored the influence of an STD

educational intervention on knowledge and attitudes related to safe sex among U.S. fraternity and sorority members²⁸. Their study showed significant improvements in safe sex-related knowledge (13.03±6.5 to 20.27±4.9, p=0.000) and demonstrated that increases in knowledge were associated with more favorable attitudes toward safe sex. Although²⁸ focused on attitudes rather than direct measurement of safe sex behaviours and addressed STDs more broadly, their results supported the broader conclusion that targeted health education leads to behavioural change or behavioural intentions conducive to safer sexual practices. The present study extended this evidence by showing not just improved attitudes but actual behaviour change, reflected in significantly higher safe sex practice scores among students who received the intervention.

The second finding of this study showed that structured health education had a meaningful influence on students' uptake of HBV vaccination. At baseline, vaccination rates were almost identical between the two groups: 10.5% of the intervention group and 9.8% of the control group had been vaccinated. This similarity confirmed that both groups were starting from comparable levels of vaccination behaviour, allowing any post-intervention differences to be attributed to the educational programme. After the intervention, the proportion of vaccinated students in the intervention group increased substantially to 30.5%, while the control group showed only a small increase to 13.7%. The resulting 17.2% difference in vaccination uptake between the two groups demonstrated that students who received structured health education were considerably more likely to initiate HBV vaccination than those who did not. This suggests that the intervention not only improved knowledge and attitudes but also successfully translated into a concrete preventive health action by beginning the vaccination process.

The Pearson chi-square analysis revealed a statistically significant association between groups and vaccination status, $\chi^2(1, N = 207) = 8.40, p = .004$. This confirmed that the difference in HBV vaccination-uptake between the intervention and control groups was not due to

chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there would be no significant difference in vaccination proportions between the two groups was rejected. Although the overall vaccination rate in the intervention group remained below 50%, the intervention achieved a meaningful increase within a relatively short period, demonstrating the potential of structured health education to stimulate the uptake of HBV vaccination among young adults.

These results can be compared with the study by²⁹, who examined the impact of a web-based educational intervention on HPV vaccination awareness, willingness, and uptake among female college students in China. Their findings similarly demonstrated that health education substantially improved knowledge and willingness to vaccinate. After seven days of web-based education, awareness, and knowledge scores in the intervention group were significantly higher than in the control group, and willingness to be vaccinated increased markedly. These results parallel the present study's finding that education can shift preventive health intentions and behaviours.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were arrived at:

1. Safe sex practices improved significantly as a result of the structured health education. The intervention group showed major improvements in behaviours that reduce the risk of HBV transmission through sexual contact, confirming the effectiveness of health education in influencing sexual health practices.
2. The intervention positively influenced HBV vaccination uptake. A notable proportion of students initiated HBV vaccination after the intervention compared with the control group, showing that health education can translate into concrete preventive health actions.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. School health units and public health educators

should incorporate structured HBV education into regular campus health programmes and orientation activities, including periodic refresher sessions to maintain and enhance students' knowledge of HBV prevention.

2. Tertiary institutions' health services and local public health departments should strengthen safe sex practices by providing ongoing sexual health education, ensuring free and accessible condom distribution, and offering confidential sexual health counselling spaces for students.
3. Tertiary institutions' health centres, in collaboration with state or local health authorities, should increase HBV vaccination uptake by organizing periodic on-site vaccination drives at subsidized or no cost, maintaining a vaccination registry, and sending reminders to students who have not completed their vaccination schedules.

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